

On the Study of Monovalent Cations by Ammonium Phosphomolybdate through Mixed Crystal Formation

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The uptake of monovalent cations has been studied with ammonium phosphomolybdate as the host and Cs^{137} , Tl^{204} , Ag^{110} , Rb^{86} , and Na^{22} as guests. Both in an internally and in an externally formed systems, the uptake has been found very high in the case of caesium and thallium. In both the cases, the uptake takes place through mixed crystal formation. In the case of rubidium as the guest, the uptake has been found to be low and chaotic. In the case of silver and sodium as guests, the extent of the uptake is still lower. In internally formed systems, the uptake follows the homogeneous distribution law in spite of the experimental conditions being in accordance with the requirements of the heterogeneous distribution factor; such an apparent anomaly is attributed to the rapid exchange. The value of the distribution factor, D , in an internally formed system is about twice that found in equilibrating the externally formed system. This discrepancy is ascribed to a difference in the morphology, depending on the mode of preparation. The time required for attainment of the equilibrium in the case of caesium is very short (20 min.) in an externally formed system, whereas in the case of thallium it takes about 17 hr. In the separation of caesium, a column of hetero-poly acid, shorter than that for thallium, will be required.

The application of hetero-poly acids in the separation of monovalent cations with special reference to caesium has been the subject matter of study for the last few years¹⁻⁵. Ammonium salts of hetero-poly acids in question are powerful inorganic ion-exchangers. The octahedral model of the anion has been suggested by some workers as a good host to accommodate any monovalent cations through mixed crystal formation. Salts of the hetero-poly acids are known to crystallise in different morphological forms, depending on the water content which varies with the mode of preparation. Data on the ion-exchange basis have been taken in externally formed salts of the hetero-poly acids where experimental condition and water of hydration considerably vary. The partition values may differ if the experimental conditions are not kept the same. Even the minimum time for the attainment of the equilibrium remains to be studied. In view of the importance involved in the separa-

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tion of the alkali metals, it is of interest to study the uptake through a coseparation mechanism both in externally and in internally formed systems to obtain a better insight of such powerful inorganic ion-exchangers.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cs¹³⁷ (carrier-free), Tl²⁰⁴, Ag¹¹⁰, and Na²² of high specific activity were supplied by Messrs Philips Duphar. Rb⁸⁶ was procured from the Atomic Energy Establishment, Trombay. A stock solution of the acid ammonium molybdate reagent was prepared as described by Treadwell and Hall¹⁶. A typical experiment is described below.

A known amount of the ammonium molybdate solution was taken in a beaker, the requisite activity added, and the solution was stirred well for a few minutes. A known volume of phosphoric acid was added dropwise from a burette. Precipitation of ammonium phosphomolybdate was conducted at 35° under constant stirring in about 1*N*-HNO₃ medium. After addition of the requisite volume of phosphoric acid, the reacting mixture was stirred for 15 min. and filtered. A portion of the filtrate was taken out by a pipette having a filter paper cap at the delivery end of it and the activity in question was measured with a glass-wall counter meant for measuring liquids. From a knowledge of the phosphoric acid added, the amount of NH₄⁺ ion precipitated as ammonium phosphomolybdate was computed. The results are recorded in Tables I and II and in Fig. 1. *D* and λ have been computed from expressions, described earlier¹⁷.

TABLE I

Distribution of some monovalent cations between internally formed ammonium phosphomolybdate and ammonium molybdate solution in N-HNO₃ medium at 35°.

Period of shaking = 15 min. Molarity of ammonium salt = 0.8648*M*.

% NH ₄ ⁺ in solid phase.	% Activity carried*.	<i>D</i> .	λ .
(a) With carrier-free caesium activity.			
0.2202	55.24	559.1	340.0
0.4129	61.07	378.4	227.7
0.8256	79.16	456.2	180.2
1.3760	88.06	529.6	153.9
		Av. 480.9	
(b) Initial caesium conc. = $1.169 \times 10^{-4}M$.			
0.2130	53.83	546.2	372.9
0.4037	68.01	524.6	291.2
0.8153	79.16	461.9	180.2
1.3640	86.83	476.8	149.2
		Av. 502.3	

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TABLE I (contd.)

% NH ₄ ⁺ in solid phase.	% Activity carried*.	D.	λ.
(c) With Tl ²⁰⁴ (of high sp. activity).			
0.2065	51.38	510.0	348.0
0.4129	70.27	570.1	292.7
0.8082	82.39	510.4	188.6
1.6510	90.87	592.8	144.4
		Av. 545.8	
(d) Initial thallium conc. = 1.69×10^{-6} M.			
0.2202	49.69	447.5	298.3
0.4129	64.20	432.5	247.8
0.8256	78.51	438.9	185.5
1.3760	84.73	397.8	136.9
		Av. 429.2	
(e) Initial thallium conc. = 1.69×10^{-5} M.			
0.2065	48.97	428.1	306.1
0.4129	65.48	457.5	256.5
0.8946	80.58	459.8	182.5
1.3760	85.60	426.0	140.3
		Av. 442.8	
(f) Initial thallium conc. = 1.69×10^{-4} M.			
0.2202	49.09	436.9	293.2
0.4129	63.54	420.5	243.4
0.8256	79.06	453.5	188.7
1.3760	86.02	478.4	147.2
		Av. 446.8	
(g) With thallium activity (of high sp. activity) in presence of ferric ion**.			
0.2477	53.46	462.5	301.8
0.4403	63.78	398.1	232.1
0.8256	76.47	390.3	174.6
1.3760	84.06	378.0	132.9
		Av. 407.2	
(h) With rubidium activity of high sp. activity.			
1.651	17.51	12.650	11.610
3.302	24.44	9.473	8.352
6.604	22.84	4.186	3.790
13.208	19.89	1.631	1.586
(i) With sodium activity (carrier free).			
18.74	1.87		
34.89	Nil		
(j) With silver activity (of high sp. activity).			
1.117	4.58		
3.384	Nil		

*Refers to Cs¹³⁷, Tl²⁰⁴, Rb⁸⁶, Ag¹¹⁰, and Na²².

**Molarity = 5.37×10^{-2} M.

TABLE II

Distribution of Cs¹³⁷ and Tl²⁰⁴ between preformed ammonium phosphomolybdate and ammonium nitrate solution in 1N-HNO₃ (ca.) medium at 35°.

Molarity of ammonium nitrate soln. = 2.18M. Shaking period = 2 days.

% NH ₄ ⁺ in solid phase.	% Cs ¹³⁷ at Tl ²⁰⁴ carried.	D.
(a) With carrier-free caesium activity.		
0.3371	45.36	245.6
0.6363	58.46	219.8
0.9051	66.93	221.6
1.0470	69.71	217.5
		Av. 226.1
(b) With Tl ²⁰⁴ (of high sp. activity).		
0.3470	42.78	214.7
0.6241	54.62	191.6
0.9164	64.83	199.3
1.0400	67.36	196.4
		Av. 200.5

N.B. Values of *D* in case of Cs¹³⁷ and Tl²⁰⁴ in internally formed systems under identical conditions are 480 and 546 respectively.

DISCUSSION

Before going into further details, attention should be drawn towards the minimum time required for the attainment of the equilibrium in preformed ammonium phosphomolybdate crystals and Cs¹³⁷ and Tl²⁰⁴ as tracers in ammonium nitrate solution. To save space both the curves have been shown in Fig. 1 in different units. In the case of caesium the equilibrium for a period shorter than 20 min. has not been studied in view of the fact that at least 15-20 min. is required for the physical processes involved in equilibration of a heterogeneous system containing 500 mg. of solid salt in a volume of 100 ml where the caesium is at a tracer level. The curve A in Fig. 1 shows that even 20 min. is sufficient to bring about the homogeneous penetration of the tracer caesium into the host lattice. The distribution values remain unchanged even on equilibration for a period of 3 days. The distribution of thallium, however, differs considerably in this respect. Curve B (Fig. 1) shows that a period of 17hr. is required for the attainment of equilibrium in the distribution of Tl²⁰⁴ in solid and solution under identical conditions. This vast difference may be due to a difference in the rates of diffusion in the two cases. In both the cases, the rate of attainment of equilibrium is, however, very quick and for this reason salts of the hetero-poly acids are regarded as ion-exchangers and their use in the separation of caesium in fission products and various process chemistry is well known. Most of the workers, who determined the *K_d* values of these hetero-poly acids, overlooked the study of the rate of exchange in such an interesting system. They rather equilibrated the system for 2 days and computed the *K_d* values. In internally formed systems, however, the rate of exchange is much quicker. In internally formed crystals, the rate of diffusion is a very quick process even in the case of thallium. Table I shows that both in the case of thallium and of caesium, the homogeneous distribution factor, *D*, is constant where the experimental conditions are

such that these demand a constancy of λ values. Probably the fineness of the crystals during the time of precipitation is responsible for such a quick rate, specially in the case of thallium. It appears from Tables I and II that the homogeneous distribution factor is much higher (about twice) in internally formed systems than those determined by equilibrating with externally formed crystals in spite of the fact that sufficient time allowed for the attainment of equilibrium in latter processes. This discrepancy may be ascribed to the hetero-poly acids crystallising with different molecules of water, depending on experimental conditions. The data in the tables also show that D is constant in the case of thallium and caesium, both in internally and externally formed systems. In the former case, the study was extended from tracer level to a finite concentration. The constancy of D leads to the conclusion that the uptake takes place through mixed crystal formation even at the tracer level.

FIG. 1 Distribution of Cs^{137} and Tl^{204} between ammonium phosphomolybdate crystal in its saturated solution in ammonium nitrate solution in LV-HNO_3 medium at 35° , showing the attainment of equilibrium.

(A) represents distribution of Cs^{137} .

(B) represents distribution of Tl^{204} .

The steps taken in the preparation of the ammonium phosphomolybdate crystals for our study in extraneously formed systems are as follows. Ammonium phosphomolybdate was prepared by adding phosphoric acid in excess of the ammonium molybdate solution in a nitric acid medium, as was done in the internally formed system. The crystals were washed with dilute nitric acid till free of the mother liquor and finally washed with ethanol. It was dried at 60° for several hours, powdered, and sieved through 120 mesh. Ammonia was analysed in the usual way by distillation and phosphate was computed by analysing molybdenum as molybdenyl oxinate. The analytical results are in good agreement with the stoichiometric ratio of the hetero-poly acids.

The peculiar behaviour observed in the case of rubidium in the internally formed systems is worth attention. It appears from Table I that the uptake is low and chaotic. Rb was expected to show also the evidence of mixed crystal formation. Probably a series of unstable hydrates is formed during the course of crystallisation of the host lattice, all of which may not be mixed crystal forming with the corresponding hydrates of rubidium. This particular aspect requires further study. In the case of our study with silver and sodium, the uptake has been found to be very low and the study in detail is not possible with such a low uptake.

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